

The Two-Phase Integration Model: A Proposed Framework of Mind–Body–Agency in Trauma Integration

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Author Note

John F. Clark is completing a Bachelor of Arts in Political Science at Washburn University. He served as a lieutenant in a women’s prison in Topeka, where he coordinated security alongside rehabilitative programs and witnessed the pervasive impact of unprocessed trauma. Drawing on three decades of personal exploration, Clark developed the **Mind–Body–Agency** Integration framework through interpretive autoethnography. His work bridges polyvagal theory, trauma literature, and transpersonal approaches to propose a structured roadmap for lasting integration. He is committed to helping others navigate their own healing journeys and aims to advance trauma integration by sharing this proposed model through clinical networks and digital platforms.

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Abstract

Grof’s “spiritual emergency” concept has not translated well into day-to-day clinical practice. This paper outlines the Two-Phase Integration Model (Mind–Body–Agency), developed through interpretive autoethnography and informed by existing trauma literature. The model distinguishes between a catalytic release (Phase 1) and subsequent integration (Phase 2), specifying three conditions that appear necessary for durable outcomes: cognitive framing, somatic safety, and volitional agency. The account is **theoretical and hypothesis-generating**

rather than empirical or validated; claims are limited to a proposed mechanism and testable predictions. The aim is not to replace existing therapies but to offer a framework that is inclusive and nuanced, helping organize current methods into a clearer sequence so they can be applied more surgically and predictably deliver lasting benefit to patients.

Keywords: spiritual emergency, trauma integration, mind-body-agency integration, cognitive framing, somatic safety, agency

See also: *Supplementary Note* (Dec 2025) for an explicit stepwise outline of the two-phase model. Steps included are only for Phase 2, trauma/material must already be conscious and emotionally available to be felt.

The Two-Phase Integration Model: A Proposed Framework of Mind–Body–Agency in Trauma Integration

Nearly forty years after Stanislav Grof’s (1985) early accounts of “spiritual emergencies,” the field still lacks clear models for how such crises can lead to lasting integration. This paper does not present new empirical data but instead proposes a **theoretical, hypothesis-generating framework** derived from interpretive autoethnography and supported where possible by existing trauma literature. The Two-Phase Integration Model (Mind–Body–Agency) is offered as a conceptual scaffold: a way to organize observations, identify testable predictions, and generate research questions about the mechanisms of integration. By explicitly distinguishing between a catalytic release (Phase 1) and a subsequent process of metabolization (Phase 2), the model seeks to clarify why integration sometimes fails and how existing therapeutic methods might be sequenced more effectively.

I propose that transformation is best conceptualized as unfolding in two phases. This is not to suggest that all cases literally occur in a fixed two-step sequence, but rather that framing the process in terms of Phase 1 (catalytic release) and Phase 2 (integration) provides a useful and coherent way to understand how crisis can become growth.

Phase 1: The Catalytic Release The first phase involves a psychophysiological event often marked by a temporary dissolution of ego structures, or ego dissolution. In this state, repressed somatic and psychic material surfaces into conscious awareness with little filtration (Nour et al., 2016). Such episodes can be intense and destabilizing, but it is important to emphasize that they represent a catalytic release rather than the healing itself.

Phase 2: Integration The second phase is the active process of metabolizing what has been unearthed. The central contribution of this paper is the proposal of three conditions that appear necessary for successful integration, synthesized in the Two-Phase Integration Model of Mind–

Body–Agency: a triad of cognitive framing, somatic safety, and ownership/agency of the healing process.

Defining Integration (Evidence-Based Clinical Criteria) Within the framework of the Two-Phase Integration Model (Mind–Body–Agency Triad), integration refers to the sustainable resolution of previously fragmented or dissociated memories, emotions, and bodily responses. These elements, once brought into conscious awareness, must be processed and reorganized into a coherent personal narrative and self-experience. Integration should not be equated with mere symptom reduction. Rather, it requires the unified engagement of cognitive understanding (mind), physiological regulation (body), and volitional agency. Integration cannot be said to occur until all three domains are active, aligned, and observable through clinical outcomes.

Criteria for Successful Integration Evidence of integration can be observed through three converging criteria:

1. **Cognitive Clarity and Narrative Coherence.** Patients demonstrate the capacity to construct sensible autobiographical narratives of the traumatic experience. The story of the trauma needs to be understood and framed into the patient’s story arc. This includes situating events in time and place with clear chronology, emotional elaboration, and resolution (Vanderveren et al., 2020). A further marker is the ability to recall traumatic memory without overwhelming distress, indicating genuine emotional processing (Brewin et al., 1996). The absence of intrusive, fragmented flashbacks and improved voluntary recall also suggest integration has occurred.
2. **Somatic Regulation and Physiological Safety** I firmly believe that both a subjective sense of safety and nervous system stability are necessary for integration. Patients need to be able to handle activation brought on by trauma without going into overwhelm or dissociation. There is evidence of a complex relationship between baseline HRV and the results of PTSD treatment. While some research indicates that a higher HF-HRV predicts a greater reduction in symptoms, which is consistent with HRV as a measure of resilience capacity, other research suggests that a "room-to-improve" effect may cause a lower resting HRV to predict more pronounced relative gains (Söder et al., 2019). Even though the exact predictive direction varies, I conclude that these findings collectively support the role of autonomic flexibility in influencing therapeutic outcomes. Several trials have reported significant effect sizes and improvements in body awareness and resilience, supporting the idea that somatic interventions, such as Somatic Experiencing, can lessen depression and PTSD symptoms (Brom et al., 2017). However, other studies in the same review did not find any significant group differences, highlighting the importance of methodological and contextual factors as well as the variability of results.
3. **Empowered Agency and Functional Restoration.** A final marker of integration is the patient’s demonstration of active, voluntary ownership of the healing process alongside restored functioning in everyday life. This extends across multiple domains: work, relationships, personal meaning, and spiritual orientation. Long-term data highlight the importance of psychological health in recovery. Rusche et al. (2025) found that 82.4% of

trauma survivors returned to employment ten years post-trauma, with mental health—not physical impairment—the strongest predictor of occupational reintegration. This reinforces the broader claim that without true psychological integration, functional restoration remains fragile. Beyond occupational recovery, integration is also reflected in measurable post-traumatic growth, including the emergence of new possibilities, improved capacity for relating to others, increased personal strength, spiritual change, and an enhanced appreciation of life (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 1996).

Conditions of Therapeutic Success Integration can be considered complete only when all three domains converge—cognitive clarity, somatic regulation, and empowered agency. Clinical research suggests that successful treatment extends beyond symptom reduction to broader functional gains (Cusack et al., 2016). At this stage, the traumatic experience remains part of the person’s history, but it no longer exerts the same destabilizing psychological or physiological effects. Instead, it is metabolized into the individual’s life narrative as one chapter among others, rather than as an ongoing disruption.

Foundations of the Model: Empirical Grounding the Two-Phase Integration Model draws on four converging lines of evidence regarding how the mind and body process threat and information.

The Narrative Self (DMN). The default mode network (DMN) underlies the narrative construction of the “self” (Buckner et al., 2008). When DMN activity decreases—as is frequently observed in altered states—self-referential filters weaken, allowing unconscious material to surface (Millière et al., 2018; Palhano-Fontes et al., 2015). This quieting of the DMN provides the opening for Phase 1, the catalytic release.

The Biology of Safety (Polyvagal Theory). The autonomic nervous system has evolved to prioritize safety cues (Porges, 2011). Establishing a ventral vagal “safe state” is a prerequisite for processing experiences that would otherwise be overwhelming (Porges, 2009).

The Felt Sense (Interoception). Interoception refers to how the nervous system interprets internal bodily signals (Craig, 2002). Integration depends on the capacity to tolerate and process the interoceptive flood that arises when unconscious material surfaces.

Resilience (HRV). Heart rate variability (HRV) provides an index of self-regulation and resilience. Optimal HRV is associated with greater regulatory capacity and signals a nervous system primed for integration (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017).

14. **The State of the Science: Methodological Limitations** The urgency of this model is heightened by gaps in the current research landscape. Standardized tools for measuring psychological integration remain limited (Aday et al., 2020). Existing studies also carry significant methodological issues, including the underreporting of adverse outcomes in clinical trials and selection bias in participant recruitment (Garcia-Romeu et al., 2015).

The Two-Phase Integration Model describes how traumatic experience may move from an unprocessed, unconscious state to one that is resolved and integrated through a sequential process.

Phase 1: The Catalytic Release (Unconscious to Conscious/Unknown) In the first phase, previously repressed or dissociated material is pushed into awareness by an event that disables ordinary psychological defenses. This event may take the form of a psychedelic experience, a meditation-related crisis (Britton et al., 2021; Farias et al., 2020), or a major life event. The underlying mechanism is ego dissolution—the temporary breakdown of ego structures (Nour et al., 2016; Millière et al., 2018). This disruption cracks the barrier of dissociation, rendering the trauma conscious, though still raw and unprocessed. The immediate consequence is often destabilization. Importantly, the simple act of bringing trauma into awareness is not itself healing. Phase 1 creates the opportunity, but integration must follow if the exposure is to be therapeutic rather than retraumatizing.

Phase 2: The Architecture of Integration In Phase 2, the task is to actively metabolize the conscious trauma. This requires transforming the raw memory into an organized, contextualized, and emotionally processed experience. Effective integration demands readiness across three domains: the cognitive (mind), the somatic (body), and the volitional agency. As van der Kolk (2014) observed, the terror and isolation at the core of trauma literally reshapes both brain and body, compromising a person's capacity for pleasure and relationships. He suggests that lasting healing is tied to the ability of trauma survivors to inhabit their bodies and tolerate their feelings.

Phase 2A: Cognitive Framework (Knowing the Trauma). Cognitive framing entails the survivor's capacity to process and make sense of what occurred. Judith Herman (1992) argued that trauma resolves only when the survivor develops a new mental schema for understanding what has happened. Through the construction of a coherent narrative, the brain can link an isolated traumatic memory with the broader autobiographical context (Brewin et al., 1996). This narrative act transforms unconscious material into explicit, known content. For example, what had once felt like an overwhelming flood of undifferentiated pain began to take on a distinct narrative form—the emotions could now be recognized as connected to earlier life experiences rather than erupting without context. Cognitive contextualization addresses the meaning of the trauma, replacing shame and confusion with structured understanding (White & Epston, 1990).

Phase 2B: Somatic Safety (Body Readiness). Integration cannot occur if the nervous system remains in a defensive state. Trauma is not only psychological but physiological; stress is stored in the body, often keeping the system in chronic hyperarousal or collapse (van der Kolk, 2014). Attempting to confront traumatic memories without physiological safety risks re-traumatization (Fisher, 2017). Establishing somatic calm is therefore critical. Neurobiologically, safety corresponds to the autonomic nervous system shifting out of survival mode, with increased ventral vagal tone allowing cognitive and emotional centers of the brain to reconnect (Porges, 2011). Somatic therapies seek to restore this regulation by enabling the discharge of pent-up survival energy (Levine, 1997; Ogden et al., 2006).

Phase 2C: Ownership/Agency. Trauma entails profound disempowerment (Herman, 1992). For this reason, effective therapy must work to reverse that helplessness through the restoration of

autonomy. As Herman (1992) observed, “She must be the author and arbiter of her own recovery” (p. 133).

Agency in this context is not reducible to a verbal affirmation only. It is better understood as an embodied capacity that signals readiness. From my understanding, it is emotional as much as it is verbal/cognitive. This stage represents the point at which the mind is prepared to know (Phase 2A) and the body is prepared to feel (Phase 2B). At that threshold, the two can converge under what may be termed a principal agency. This idea resonates with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which emphasizes autonomy—acting with volition and self-endorsement—as a core requirement for authentic change (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Phase 2C therefore functions as the catalyst, the active volition that allows mind and body to meet and co-process the traumatic material.

13. **The Emergent Property: Integration.** The traumatic memory can be reprocessed through emotional processing and extinction learning when cognitive framing, somatic safety, and empowered agency come together (Foa et al., 2007). By this time, the psychological impact of the incident has diminished. Rather, it is absorbed into the larger story of their life—remembered and understood, but without the same disrupting influence (Brewin et al., 1996). I find that the best way to think of integration is as a three-gated system: **cognition, body, and agency.** The process is rarely linear due to the very messy nature trauma intertwines with the human experience. I reinforce however, each gate still needs to be unlocked. The procedure appears more like a circuit that only illuminates when all three gates are open simultaneously than a formula.

Table 1

Comparison of Existing Trauma/Mystical Experience Models vs. Two-Phase Integration Model

Framework / Theory	What It Explains	What It Misses	How Two-Phase Integration Model Fills the Gap
Herman’s 3-Phase Trauma Model (1992)	Phases: Safety → Remembrance/Mourning → Reconnection. Widely cited in PTSD treatment.	Describes therapeutic stages but doesn’t specify neurobiological mechanisms or why trauma “gets stuck.”	Maps safety (Phase 2B) to autonomic readiness (polyvagal/HRV), remembrance to cognitive framing (Phase 2A), and reconnection to explicit ownership/permission (Phase 2C).
Somatic Experiencing / Body-Oriented Trauma Therapies (Levine, Ogden)	Show how trauma persists in the body and emphasize somatic release.	Often lack emphasis on meaning-making or narrative frameworks; can result in catharsis without integration.	Pairs somatic readiness with conceptual framing, ensuring body discharge is contextualized and translated into integration.

Framework / Theory	What It Explains	What It Misses	How Two-Phase Integration Model Fills the Gap
Ego Dissolution / Psychedelic Research (Carhart-Harris, Millière)	Demonstrates how DMN downregulation surfaces unconscious material.	Stops short at describing <i>what happens next</i> once unconscious material is conscious but unprocessed.	Identifies Phase 2 as the crucial integration process requiring cognitive + somatic alignment.
Mindfulness Mechanisms (Hölzel et al., 2011)	Attention regulation, body awareness, emotion regulation, perspective shift.	Focuses on processes during practice but doesn't formalize pre-integration surges or explain failed integration outcomes.	Explains why mindfulness "works" only if the three prerequisites (cognitive frame, somatic safety, ownership) converge.
Neurovisceral Integration Model (Thayer & Lane, 2000)	Links HRV to self-regulation and emotional adaptability.	Doesn't specify sequencing of trauma surfacing → integration, or role of explicit permission.	Provides the physiological rationale for Phase 2B (somatic readiness), embedded in a larger two-phase sequence.
General Ritual Research (Hobson et al., 2018)	Shows rituals scaffold altered states, reduce threat signaling, and shape meaning.	Explains <i>how</i> rituals work but not <i>why</i> experiences predictably unfold in two phases.	Situates rituals as cultural "technologies" that trigger Phase 1 release and Phase 2 consolidation.
Proposed Two-Phase Integration Framework (Clark, 2025)	Explicitly formalizes: Phase 1 (unconscious surfacing, DMN downregulation, somatic flooding); Phase 2 (integration). Sub-phases: 2A cognitive framing, 2B somatic readiness, 2C ownership/permission.	n/a	May provide the first mechanistic roadmap uniting phenomenology, neuroscience, and therapy into a replicable sequence.

Figure 1

Two-Phase Integration Model

Note. Phase 1 brings unconscious trauma into conscious memory through a triggering event. Phase 2 can now transform the now-conscious material through cognitive framing, somatic regulation, and personal agency, resulting in resolution. Phase 2 subcomponents can occur and vary in order, but I hypothesize all three must be fulfilled before moving to the Integration Stage.

Methodology and Case Illustration: An Interpretive Autoethnographic Account My Two-Phase Integration Model was created through an interpretive autoethnographic inquiry (Ellis et al., 2011) in which the myself as the researcher systematically examined my own experience of spiritual emergency and subsequent recovery. I believe, autoethnography is well suited to this article, since subjective phenomenology can reveal internal unique processes that are often unseen through standard research. The identification of the proposed framework's core components emerged directly from journaling and self-reflection. These data provided the phenomenological foundation for a testable hypothesis, later supported by trauma literature. As a single-case inquiry, I cannot prove it empirically, but I do hope it serves as a theoretically grounded starting point for further inquiry.

Ethical Considerations This autoethnographic work was conducted in line with established ethical guidelines for self-study research (Ellis et al., 2011). Because it involved only the researcher's own experience, and no additional participants, Institutional Review Board approval was not required. Even so, careful attention was given to the ethical dimensions of publicly sharing personal trauma material, particularly the potential emotional impact on readers.

Background In 2018, I reached a point where I felt completely overwhelmed by grief I hadn't even realized I was carrying. It felt as though something had stopped me in my tracks. Looking back, this moment fits what Grof and Grof (1989) called a "spiritual emergency," but at the time I had no framework for understanding what was happening to me.

I was doing ordinary work in my garage—nothing special, nothing that should have triggered such a reaction. Then an overwhelming wave of grief came over me. I collapsed onto the concrete floor, sobbing so hard I couldn't catch my breath and with absolutely no idea why it felt so enormous or where it was coming from.

With my eyes squeezed shut, something strange happened. I felt a presence—warm and encompassing, as if I were being wrapped in a blanket and gently rocked, as one would do with a frightened child. At the time, I was convinced it was God. I thought I'd been chosen for something, given some kind of spiritual mission. That interpretation felt so real and meaningful that I held onto it for years. But here's the thing: if someone had been filming me that day, they wouldn't have seen any divine visitation. They would have seen a middle-aged man collapsed on his garage floor, arms wrapped around himself, rocking back and forth. What felt like a divine embrace was my own nervous system doing what it needed—self-soothing in a way I didn't yet understand.

The problem was, I couldn't accept that this ocean of grief belonged to me. It felt too big, too much. So, I made it about everyone else—collective human suffering, cosmic pain, anything except my own unprocessed trauma. That refusal to own it became the point where everything got stuck. Without ownership, I couldn't make sense of what had happened. And without making sense of it, nothing could move forward.

I stayed stuck for years. It wasn't until I started ketamine therapy (under clinical supervision) that something shifted. Ketamine gave me just enough distance from my usual defenses to see my life differently. Suddenly, memories I had buried started surfacing the whole messy catalog of childhood trauma I'd spent decades avoiding. Suddenly, I realized that the garage breakdown wasn't some mystical experience. It was my psyche finally processing decades of pain.

Even after the cognitive breakthrough, I didn't feel healed. If anything, I felt worse. Finally naming what had happened gave me clarity, but it also unleashed a flood of emotion. The sadness deepened, and with it came layers of anger and grief I hadn't been able to access before. Knowing the truth was better than not knowing, but it didn't bring relief on its own.

The next phase emerged almost by accident. In searching for relief, I stumbled upon somatic relief. What began with something as simple as listening to ASMR online unexpectedly shifted my state. For reasons I could not have predicted, it worked. The oxytocin release brought on by those experiences gave the first sense of safety. From there I experimented further, combining oxytocin nasal spray with breathwork and music that framed and held my grief. Through that process, my nervous system gradually learned it was safe to relax. The constant "alarm bells" began to quiet.

This somatic readiness opened the door for the final step: ownership. It was not enough to understand cognitively, or even to feel safe in the body. Integration required an active decision—a conscious commitment to take responsibility for the healing process itself. Only with this commitment did the three domains converge into something that felt complete.

The sequence wasn't linear—I bounced around between cognitive insights, somatic breakthroughs, and moments of clarity about my own agency. But those three elements were all essential. I think of them as gates now: cognitive understanding, somatic safety, and conscious choice. If any one of them remains locked, the whole process stalls.

That's why I believe this model could be useful in clinical practice. Right now, trauma therapy often feels random—one technique after another, hoping something will work. But if we understand that integration requires these three specific elements, we can be much more strategic. Instead of trying random approaches, we can focus directly on unlocking the specific gates that remain locked.

Case Analysis

Phase 1: Unconscious Material Surfacing The event came as "a profound wave of grief... decades of suppressed sorrow flooding my chest and throat." At the time, there was no sense of what was happening. It simply felt like the saddest moment of a lifetime, with no explanation for

why it felt so enormous. The only certainty was the intensity itself. Looking back, this was an involuntary interoceptive surge—trauma forcing its way into awareness despite the absence of any prior recognition. The event coincided with a felt dissolution of self, a temporary collapse of the ordinary frame of reference, which allowed raw material to surface without the usual mediation of language or thought.

Phase 2: Conscious Integration and Meaning-Making Integration unfolded in a way that closely reflected the three-part structure of the model.

- **Cognitive Framework (2A).** After thousands of hours of journaling and self-reflection, a consistent pattern began to show itself: there was an immense amount of unprocessed childhood trauma that had until then remained completely unknown to me. When I engaged in the act of naming this truth shifted the material from being “conscious but unrecognized” to “conscious and known.” That recognition—however stark and debilitating—became the intellectual ground on which further integration could occur.
- **Somatic Readiness (2B).** As time passed, My nervous system slowly settled, and my body began to feel safe enough to stay with the grief rather than recoil from it. This safety (often I found was elusive) was not instant; it came in waves, in small increments, until there was enough stability to hold what surfaced. Only then could the grief be metabolized instead of overwhelming.
- **Explicit Permission and Ownership (2C).** My final step came as an active decree of ownership. I allowed my body to begin the release, while my mind stayed present to contextualize what emerged. Texts and self-help mantra’s often insist on “surrendering”. It was not so much as admitting defeat but stating that I am no longer holding resistance and decide to actively author my own healing. I decided to no longer ascribe to outsourcing the experience, and not to bypass it to something cosmic or external. My grief was claimed, and in that simple act of agency, the raw emotion began to take shape as coherent meaning and allow the destabilization to fade away. It was a visceral and an experience I will remember for the rest of my entire life.

Outcomes My own personal lived sequence mirrored this model’s logic, and with it came lasting relief. While this is a single case and I cannot speak to general patterns on its own, it does provide the phenomenological foundation for the hypothesis—one that was later tested against and strengthened by engagement with the wider trauma literature.

Discussion: Proposed Framework the Two-Phase Integration Model may help address some of the methodological limitations that continue to shape the study of altered states and trauma (Aday et al., 2020; Wright et al., 2024). It offers a sequenced, testable framework that seeks to bridge transpersonal phenomenology with contemporary neuroscience. Whereas existing approaches often describe recovery elements in parallel, this proposed framework suggests that cognition, embodiment, and agency may need to align in temporal sequence if integration is to endure.

The delineation of the Phase 2 triad emerged from a synthesis of autoethnographic data and an inductive review of established trauma modalities that integration appears to require the convergence of mind, body, and agency. The three domains appear interdependent and mutually

reinforcing; integration seems to arise only when they converge in what might be described as embodied coherence (Vanderveren et al., 2020).

When this coherence is present, individuals often demonstrate what could be called flexible resilience—the ability to move through a broad range of emotional states without becoming overwhelmed or disconnected (Söder et al., 2019). Survivors themselves tend to put it simply: the traumatic event “still happened and still matters,” but it no longer “runs their life” or automatically triggers defensive responses. Instead, they describe being able to “hold the pain and the growth together” (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 1996).

The importance of the triad becomes more visible when its absence is considered. Partial approaches seem to clarify why fragmented interventions often fail to yield lasting change:

- ***Cognition without Embodiment (2A without 2B)***. This tends to result in intellectualization—a narrative understanding that remains detached from physiological regulation. Without somatic safety, cognitive insight may remain disconnected from lived experience (Ogden et al., 2006; van der Kolk, 2014; Brom et al., 2017).
- ***Embodiment without Meaning (2B without 2A)***. This can lead to catharsis without context. Without a coherent autobiographical frame, affect may remain raw, unprocessed, and vulnerable to re-triggering (Brewin et al., 1996; Vanderveren et al., 2020).
- ***Intervention without Agency (neglecting 2C)***. Interventions that bypass embodied agency risk compliance rather than empowerment. In such cases, the fundamental disempowerment of trauma arguably remains unresolved. A range of research supports the claim that autonomous engagement is essential for genuine change (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Herman, 1992; Ryan & Deci, 2017).

The efficacy of the model seems to rest on this synergy. It is arguably the convergence of knowing, feeling, and willing that enables traumatic experience to be metabolized into restored function. Rusche et al. (2025) report that 82.4% of individuals who achieved integration successfully returned to employment, with mental health being a central determinant of this occupational reintegration—a finding that may underscore the practical relevance of the triadic framework.

Figure 2

Conceptual Venn diagram of integration pathways.

Note. This figure illustrates how diverse trauma therapies map onto the proposed framework of Cognitive Framing (2A), Somatic Safety (2B), and Agency/Ownership (2C). Placement within the diagram does not imply that any single intervention guarantees a given outcome; rather, interventions often bleed across domains, supporting more than one aspect of integration to varying degrees. I propose that successful and lasting integration is most likely when an individual can affirmatively answer the diagnostic questions associated with each sub-phase. See below

Clinical Implications and Sequencing the Two-Phase Integration Model may provide both diagnostic and therapeutic roadmaps for transpersonal and trauma-informed practice. By assessing readiness across the three domains, clinicians can arguably apply more targeted interventions in sequence rather than relying on scattershot methods.

Diagnostic Assessment Clinicians can tentatively evaluate integration readiness by assessing each domain:

- **Cognitive Readiness (2A).** Does the patient appear able to construct coherent autobiographical accounts about their experience? Do they show some capacity for meaning-making without becoming overwhelmed?
- **Somatic Readiness (2B).** Is there evidence of measurable autonomic stability (e.g., improved HRV, reduced hyperarousal)? Can the client, to some extent, tolerate emotional activation without slipping into dissociation?
- **Volitional Readiness (2C).** Does the client seem to demonstrate ownership of their healing process? Are they engaging from intrinsic motivation rather than compliance?

Categorical Intervention Strategy This framework emphasizes that all three domains of integration—cognitive reframing (2A), somatic regulation (2B), and permission/ownership (2C)—theoretically must be addressed. The order can change depending on the individual's process, but integration appears incomplete until each category has been fulfilled. For example, attempts at meaning-making without somatic stability may remain fragile, while somatic work without eventual coherent mental framing can leave the material untethered (**Brewin et al., 1996; Ogden et al., 2006**).

Transpersonal Applications

- **Ritual Design.** Sacred practices could be intentionally structured to facilitate Phase 1 release (e.g., guided breathwork, movement) followed by integration protocols that address all three domains in sequence.
- **Integration Circles.** Group processes may benefit from explicitly assessing readiness in each domain, with tailored interventions ranging from narrative therapy for cognitive framing to biofeedback for somatic regulation.
- **Training Requirements.** Transpersonal practitioners arguably require training in autonomic regulation methods and trauma-informed agency practices to provide safe and effective integration support.

Treatment Outcome Expectations. Evidence shows that while trauma-focused therapies like CPT and Prolonged Exposure can lead to clinically meaningful symptom improvement, many patients continue to meet diagnostic criteria. For example, Steenkamp et al. (2015) reported that between 60% and 72% of patients retained their PTSD diagnosis after treatment, underscoring the need for more effective and personalized interventions.

- **Limitations and Future Directions** While the Two-Phase Integration Model offers a novel framework for understanding spiritual emergencies and trauma integration, several limitations warrant acknowledgment and suggest directions for further study.

Methodological Constraints My autoethnographic origin while rich with applicability only represents a single-case study, and its generalizability is very limited. Although the model appears to align with established trauma literature, systematic empirical validation across diverse populations. Data that is gathered in retrospect is evidently flawed and could have inaccuracies due to the subjective nature of experience as time changes everyone's perception my own notwithstanding.

Measurement and Cultural Validity Neurobiological studies and psychometric tools in current use often carry cultural bias (Mosurinjoh et al., 2023), raising concerns about whether findings around the DMN, HRV, and polyvagal theory can be generalized across settings. My model will likely require validation in a variety of cultural contexts and spiritual traditions before claims of universal applicability can be made.

Empirical Validation

Several research priorities emerge:

- ***Longitudinal Neurophysiological Studies.*** Real-time tracking of DMN dynamics, HRV patterns, and autonomic markers across both phases could empirically validate the model's neural predictions.
- ***Randomized Integration Trials.*** Comparative studies of different Phase 2 interventions (cognitive-only vs. somatic-only vs. full triad approaches) are needed to demonstrate the model's clinical superiority.
- ***Psychometric Development.*** Creation of a standardized Two-Phase Integration Scale could address the current absence of integration-specific measurement tools.
- ***Cross-Cultural Investigation.*** Studies examining how different ritual and therapeutic traditions map onto the three-domain framework across diverse populations.
- ***Individual Difference Factors.*** Research into how personality variables, trauma history, and neurobiological differences moderate integration trajectories.

Theoretical Scope Considerations The framework focuses primarily on nervous system mechanisms but could benefit from expanded consideration of sociocultural, environmental, and relational factors that influence integration outcomes. While my proposed framework addresses spiritual emergencies broadly, specific applications to different types of mystical experiences (psychedelic, meditative, spontaneous) require further description.

Conclusion The Two-Phase Integration Model, which provides a suggested mechanistic framework to explain why spiritual emergencies and trauma crises frequently seem to follow predictable two-stage patterns, may be a significant theoretical advancement in transpersonal psychology. The model, which combines more recent findings from neuroscience, polyvagal theory, somatic intelligence research, and embodied cognition with Stanislav Grof's original

phenomenological observations, is positioned as a testable framework that may be able to close an explanatory gap that has existed for more than 40 years.

Its central claim—that integration necessitates volitional agency, somatic safety, and cognitive framing—offers theoretical coherence as well as possible therapeutic benefits. The unconscious surge of phase 1, which is characterized by ego dissolution and DMN downregulation, may set the stage for transformation, but it is not healing in and of itself. With the help of autonomic stabilization and embodied meaning-making, Phase 2's conscious integration appears to convert that content into quantifiable results reported in the literature, including improved function, post-traumatic growth, physiological regulation, and restored narrative coherence.

By implying that although subjectively profound, numinous experiences could result from the nervous system's innate ability to self-regulate and heal, this framework also advances transpersonal psychology. Such a viewpoint could honor both the transformative nature of mystical experience and the biological processes that seem to enable transformation, bridging spiritual and scientific explanations without reducing one to the other.

The model seems to offer a diagnostic road map for clinical practice that shifts away from haphazard interventions and toward more systematic procedures. Practitioners may choose to evaluate integration readiness and implement evidence-based interventions that open the required "gates" for healing rather than depending on eclectic approaches in the hopes that they will eventually yield results.

There are many prospects for future research. These could include cross-cultural analyses of the efficacy of rituals, randomized trials comparing integration protocols, and neuroimaging studies that monitor integration processes in real time. The development of standardized assessment instruments may therefore change the way integration outcomes are assessed and encouraged. In the end, the Two-Phase Integration Model suggests a method of redefining spiritual crises as potentially predictable, integrable catalysts for human transformation rather than as unexplainable anomalies. It may improve transpersonal psychology's theoretical complexity and clinical efficacy by providing a testable framework with practice-oriented guidance. This could help reshape the field's understanding of and approach to the process of moving from spiritual emergency to sustained growth.

Addendum: Explicit Procedural Steps for the Two-Phase Model of (Conscious) Trauma Resolution

For clarity and future operationalization, this addendum outlines a sequence of explicit procedural steps implied by the two-phase model of conscious trauma resolution described above. Under appropriate conditions, these steps may be both necessary and sufficient to rapidly reduce the distress associated with a specific, consciously accessible wound. The language is intentionally generic, allowing these steps to be applied across diverse modalities (e.g., psychotherapeutic dialogue, somatic therapies, pharmacologically assisted sessions, or evocative media such as music).

1. Precise contextualization and targeting of the wound

The first requirement is the establishment of a clear cognitive-affective “container” for the traumatic material. The individual is guided to identify, as specifically as possible, the type of wound being addressed (for example, chronic emotional neglect, abandonment, disenfranchised grief, humiliation, or threat to survival) and to formulate a description of it in language that elicits a direct somatic response upon contemplation. In practice, the criterion is that this description feels experientially ‘true’ and is sufficiently specific that the person’s autonomic nervous system reacts when they engage with it.

This step serves to differentiate the targeted wound from more diffuse distress and to organize the activated memory–affect network. It also provides a stable narrative frame within which the subsequent emotional activation can be processed (or metabolized).

2. Evocation of the traumatic affective response

Once the target has been defined, the individual is supported in deliberately revisiting the wound so that the associated affect can arise in conscious awareness. This evocation can occur via imaginal exposure, therapeutic dialogue, the recall of specific memories, symbolically resonant material, or structured stimuli (such as music) that reliably evoke the relevant emotional theme. One clear marker that the correct material has been accessed is that the intensity of the emotional reaction becomes disproportionate to the immediate present-moment cue. In these instances, the response reflects the accumulated, repeated trauma rather than the current situation alone.

The aim of this step is not mere re-exposure but the activation of the bound affect in a context where it can be processed rather than re-enacted.

3. Maintenance of anchoring within the window of tolerance

Concurrent with the emotional evocation, the individual must remain anchored within a tolerable arousal range (i.e., within their “window of tolerance”). In practical terms, this means having some form of internal or external anchor present (for example, the steady presence of a regulating therapist or trusted companion, grounding sensory cues, or another stabilizing focus) to help keep the individual partially oriented to present safety while the traumatic material is being felt.

This anchoring is essential to prevent the nervous system from shifting into either hypoarousal (numbing, shutdown, dissociation) or hyperarousal (overwhelming panic or rage), states which would interrupt the processing. The key task in this step is to titrate the exposure so that the individual feels the wound enough for it to be metabolized, while still staying grounded in the safety of the present moment.

4. Explicit naming of the core experiential truth

As the individual remains anchored and feels the activated pain, they are invited to name, in their own words, the core truth of the experience. This might take the form of statements such as “This is the pain of being abandoned,” “This is the terror of not surviving,” or “This is the shame of being seen as unworthy.” The exact wording is less important than the subjective sense that the formulated statement accurately captures the essence of what is being felt and that the body “recognizes” this truth.

This explicit naming functions as a semantic-somatic alignment process. In other words, the verbal expression and the embodied emotional state are brought into synchrony. This alignment provides a precise container that allows the nervous system to organize around the truth of the experience rather than around defensive distortions.

5. Ownership of the wound as one’s own internal material

Once the pain has been accurately named, the individual is guided to adopt an active stance of ownership. This involves a shift from experiencing the wound solely as something that happened to them, to recognizing it as something that now exists within their own system and is therefore within their sphere of agency. In simple language, this can be expressed as: “This is my pain; it lives in me now.”

Taking ownership does not negate or minimize the original harm or the context in which it occurred. Rather, it reframes the task at hand. While the past cannot be changed, the residual emotional charge can now be acknowledged as part of the individual’s internal world in the present. It thus becomes something they have permission to tend, influence, and ultimately release.

6. Conscious permission for completion and release

From this stance of ownership, the individual is invited to give explicit internal permission for their nervous system to complete its adaptive response and to release the bound emotional charge associated with the targeted wound. This permission may be

articulated internally or aloud in phrases such as “I allow this pain to move,” “I allow this to complete,” or “I allow my body to let go of this.” The specific wording can vary; the key is explicitly allowing completion and release, rather than continued holding.

When all of the preceding conditions have been met (clear contextualization, adequate anchoring in the window of tolerance, accurate naming, and genuine ownership), this final step is often followed by a relatively rapid shift in the individual’s subjective state. Individuals often report a sense of relief, lightness, or the feeling of “something lifting,” along with observable changes in autonomic tone (e.g., spontaneous sighs, shifts in posture, softening of musculature). As a result, the previously disproportionate reactivity associated with the original trigger tends to diminish markedly in subsequent encounters.

John F. Clark, December 9, 2025

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